

How Social Media Affects College Students Psychological, Physical, and Social Well-being

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11551742

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton
May 2024

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Date:

5/15/2024

5/24/2024

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Abstract

According to Concordia University, today's generation of college students has grown up with social media easily at hand, which entices them to spend an average of 4.5 hours on the media per day. Research from the US Department of Health and Human Services indicates that within the past couple of years, there has been a vast increase in psychological, physical, and social consequences attributed directly to the time spent on social media. College students remain widely consumed by social media used for more than just conversing with others online; it's been taken to an entirely new extreme. The American College Health Association includes insights on how social media intake can harm college students due to the time and energy spent on these online platforms. In the current study, different aspects of social usage will be discussed, along with the role social media plays in a college student's everyday life, indicating that there is adequate data to suggest a connection. To gain data from a primary source, a survey was conducted with college students (18-22 years old) attending California State University, Fullerton. Students completed a self-report questionnaire that measured anxiety, depression, cyberbullying, body image, and overall media usage. With the primary data collected and the context offered by a plethora of published articles, the findings offer correlations to support given hypotheses, emphasize conclusions, and confirm inferences. In conclusion, a strong positive connection remains between the time spent on social media and the impact on college students.

Introduction

Defining Social Media Usage

It is no surprise that social media has become much more popular than ever before in recent years. Social media has shaped the way we interact with each other, behave and learn. With the click of a button and the advancement of technology, everything is right in front of our faces. Social Media can be a great collaborative and creative space for all content creation, from blog posts to podcasts to videos. Given post-pandemic times, social media has become an addiction and a central part of our everyday lives today, especially for teenagers and young adults; it remains our go-to, safe space. Given the COVID-19 pandemic, our screen time has tremendously increased and become a central communication medium amongst friends, family, celebrities, athletes and even influencers. Altering who we are as individuals to fit into unrealistic social standards seen online. Social media has played a vital role in the increase in mental health issues among the college student population, leading to an increased risk of depression and anxiety (Lim, 2022). Being at the forefront of discussion, mental health decline from social media has become a more significant issue to address and a critical aspect to research. Through comparison of what they see posted online, individuals are now more than ever before trying to fit into this unrealistic, fake beauty standard, leading to an increase in cyberbullying, as well as increasing factors of social comparison and social anxiety (Lam, 2022). The following literature review will examine how social media affects the psychological, physical, and social aspects of a college student's well-being—while addressing how each factor plays a detrimental role in how students perceive themselves and interact with others.

Literature Review

Psychological Responses to Social Media

There has been a clear relationship between social media and the psychological impact it can have. With the recent rise of digital media becoming more prevalent, we begin to see the impact especially with college students. With all the information out today, including personal surveys to gain additional insight, it is easy to see the impact of active social media use on college students. The prevalence of social anxiety in college students is anywhere between 7-33% worldwide. For these students, if their anxiety is not improved, it may lead to a severe social anxiety disorder that may affect their academic performance, career development, and mental health (Lai et al., 2023). As this large number continues to grow, we can see a more considerable impact at hand. According to this study, researchers were able to confirm that social anxiety issues developed from a combination of personal, external, and other factors such as gender, family income, personality traits, and individual upbringing (Lai et al., 2023). The lower the family income, the higher the level of social anxiety; similarly with gender, female students perceived a higher level of social anxiety due to the self-construction theory that men and women have different understandings of self-awareness.

Furthermore, in a 2012 study by the American College Health Association, 32.9% of college students stated that they had been diagnosed with or treated with a mental health-related issue such as anorexia, panic attacks, and most commonly depression (ACHA, 2012). Today, we can only imagine this percentage has climbed and is becoming an even larger obstacle to address. Cross-sectional research consistently shows that there is indeed a relationship between college students' social media use and increased depression and anxiety (Murrieta et al., 2018). Depression seen in college students would more likely put these individuals at moderate risk of being a compulsive social media user rather than a moderate risk pleasure social media users. In the case of problematic social media use, mental distress, such as depression, emerges as a

significant predisposing factor (Cui, et al., 2014). With the wide variety of articles and data published, researchers have been able to see the high prevalence of mental distress among college students, indicating that there is a valid relationship. Those already experiencing mental distress are more prone to developing problematic use of social media, indicating that these two factors are interchangeable and may be dependent on one another. Further, many college students with mental health conditions are not seeking the help they desperately need due to the stigma they could face from family, friends, as well as other students (Martin, 2010). This leads to more undiagnosed cases, as they work on eliminating the risk of confrontation and protecting their self-image. But with this issue, studies have shown that many students turned to social media to find the support they desperately need through various platforms (Vornholt, 2021). In essence, social media can be seen as an escape while meeting the needs of students currently struggling, potentially making factors worse.

Physical Effects of Social Media

Those who spend larger amounts of time on the media are more likely to be emotionally invested and experience more of a negative impact on multiple factors, ranging from a decrease in social wellness, higher levels of depression, lower self-esteem, body dissatisfaction, and eating disorders (Woods et al., 2016). This has led to an increase in a negative self-body image of oneself, as individuals are invested in evaluating the weight and shape of one's body online. The impact of these issues has been seen clearly on social networking platforms, from uploading photos and seeking negative feedback, exposure to "thin-ideal" influencers, and, most broadly, social appearance comparison, with an indirect effect on body dissatisfaction (NIH, 2021). It has been reported that social media is one of the factors contributing to overall body dissatisfaction,

as viewing posts of others on social media directly correlated to social comparison, leading to a decrease in love for one's own body (Rousseau et al., 2017).

Restrained eating behavior is prevalent among college students; it is estimated that over 7.65 million individuals are involved in restrained eating (Yang, 2021). Long-term exposure to the media can increase feelings of isolation, anxiety, and media internalized pressures (Ouyang, 2021). In relation to body dissatisfaction, there remains shame and stress of what the ideal body shape looks like that's promoted in the media. In past studies, there has been a common theme of idealizing what a slim, perfect body on television looks like, increasing the likelihood, especially in women, of having an eating disorder (Mills, 2002). This affects young women who attempt to create and desire the ideal body shape based on what is seen online. Perceiving that the body figure online is inconsistent with reality ultimately affects body esteem. It is likely to trigger restrained eating to achieve this ideal figure (Karacan, 2014). Researchers have confirmed that internalized media pressures were possibly related to additional restrained eating behaviors in college students (Fu, 2022). The media demonstrating what the ideal body shape looks like has led to this internalized pressure for individuals to change their eating habits to fit this unrealistic standard, making them more susceptible to self-objectification.

Social Effects of Social Media

Social media has provided numerous positive opportunities for young individuals to connect and share their thoughts with others online. However, this double-edged sword of seeking the media to comfort those who feel the same way can also be dangerous. The demand to fit into these fake, unrealistic beauty standards we see today in the media has had an apparent effect on physical and psychological health. Media today is used to compare ourselves to one

another, leading to a tremendous increase in cyberbullying happening on all social media platforms, resulting in more problems than benefits. Cyberbullying victimization moderates the relationship between social comparison and social anxiety (Lam, 2022). Cyberbullying can be anything from direct threats or verbal assaults to posting an inappropriate photo of the victim without proper consent. This issue is becoming more common today because it's easier to create a fake account and leave hate comments than to speak to an individual directly. Having a screen for protection leaves individuals more inclined to say hurtful things than if they were physically present. College students' cyberbullying perpetrators had more issues with problematic social media use, meaning these students have the urge to spend too much time on social media, which can damage real-life relationships (Kircaburun et al., 2018). A fundamental study shows that young adults between the age of 18-29 years old have the highest active engagement on social media, leading to a higher increase in experiencing cyberbullying (Pew Research Center, 2022). College students with a lack of social and communication skills appear as easy targets who are unlikely to retaliate, demonstrating that these individuals are at a higher risk of being bullied online (Navarro et al., 2011). Results show that these bullies will likely not possess adequate social skills or emotional intelligence outside of the media (Lam, 2022). Cyberbullying and victimization are prevalent in the daily lives of a large number of individuals in the current digital age (Ding et al., 2020).

Mid-Western University has done a recent study to sample college students using at least one form of a networking website, in which they were able to identify that there remains a higher percentage of females than males in the media. Later studies indicate no significant difference in effects between the two genders (Gerlich, 2010). In general, most students use social media for entertainment (95%), to stay up to date on the news (88%), and to socialize (85%) (AlFaris et al.,

2018). In general, popularity on social media is a status symbol that provides identity validation based on the number of likes or followers one may have. A recent study found that over 18% of a US-based college student sample reports some sort of cyberbullying victimization when using social media sites (Whittaker, 2022). It has also been noticed that college student victims who reported being cyberbullied on social media indicate that they have either confronted the perpetrator or stayed offline to protect themselves from further victimization (Mendeley, 2016). One noted that experiencing any sort of cyberbullying through social media can impact the perspectives of social relationships and belonging (Kowalski, 2022).

Current Study

This research strengthens the possibility of a greater understanding of the effects social media can have on individuals, specifically with the target audience of college students. Furthermore, social media usage in college students affects all subsections of physical, psychological, and social aspects, with some areas being affected more than others, as research examines. Regardless, this literature review has addressed different dimensions of mental health, physical health, anxiety, depression, cyberbullying, social usage, and body image. Allowing valuable insight and acknowledgment enables us to make positive relationships among the negative impact social media has on college students through each of these dimensions. To further this research and gain more profound data, four different hypotheses were created relating to the main research question that has been used to test these theories on real-life test subjects to see the drastic impact firsthand.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Social media usage impacts the mental health of college students by increasing symptoms of anxiety to depression.

Hypothesis 2: An increase in social media usage has negatively impacted our body image.

Hypothesis 3: With social media readily available at the fingertips of college students, there has been an increase in cyberbullying.

Hypothesis 4: Increased social media use will correlate with a decrease in college students' overall morale.

Methodology

A literature review was analyzed using the Pollack Library database at California State University, Fullerton, using keywords to help kickstart the discovery of accurate sources. The search was conducted and strengthened by using peer-reviewed articles written to help address the effects of Based on the literature review, I conducted a survey where students from California State University, Fullerton, had the opportunity to participate and fill out a 20-30 minute survey addressing Social Media Usage, Body Image, Depression, Anxiety, and Cyberbullying. The data collected have been explored intently, and the results helped me gain personal insight into the main question at hand while addressing the hypotheses developed and making new observations from these results.

Participants

A total of 150 students ranging between the ages of 18 and 27 participated in the study. Most participants were undergraduate students ranging in age from first-year to fourth-year, with very few graduate student responses. Data consisted of 59 male-identifying students and 91 female-identifying students. Out of the 150 participants, the racial/ethnic breakdown was 48% Latinx, 30% Asian, 14% White, 7% two or more races, 1% African American, and 1% Native Hawaiian. 51% of the participants were first-year students, followed by 20% in their second

year, 14% in their third year, and 13% in their fourth year. With this sample size, 57% of students had a job, working between 1-43 hours per week and maintaining an annual income of up to \$20,000. Furthermore, this sample was enrolled in anywhere between 4 to 24 units this semester.

Measures

The Body Image Scale

The Body Image Scale (Rowe, D. (2018) BSIQ) measures individuals' view of body image by asking a series of questions. The BSIQ is a 27-item scale to address overall feelings on images, feelings, and thoughts. Items are scored on a 1-5 point scale, with Not at all true of myself (a)=1, Slightly true of myself (b)=2, About halfway true of myself (c)=3, Mostly true of myself (d)=4, and Completely true of myself (e)=5. With the exception of question 1 being reverse-coded. The subscales are OAE = Overall Appearance Evaluation; HFI = Health Fitness Influence; II = Investment in Ideals; HFE = Health-Fitness Evaluation; AG = Attention to Grooming; HD = Height Dissatisfaction; FE = Fatness Evaluation; NA = Negative Affect; SD = Social Dependence. The total score reflects an individual's degree of negative body image.

The Social Networking Usage Questionnaire

The Social Networking Usage Questionnaire (Gupta, S., Bashir, L. (2018) SNUQ) measures individuals' social networking usage along an array of dimensions. It is part of a factor structure that comprises 5 factors addressing questions relating to academics (7 questions), socialization (6 questions), entertainment (4 questions), informativeness (3 questions), and constraints (4 questions). These questions and factors are presented in a chart where individuals

can mark their responses using the 5-point Likert scale as follows, “Always=5, Often=4, Sometimes=3, Rarely=2, Never=1”. From their score, we can then calculate individual overall ratings and compare results to the total sum of 25.

Depression Scale

The Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale (Radloff, L. (1977) CES-D-R-10) measures an individual's depression level. The 10 questions aim to get individuals participating in the study to express how they feel and behave. Each question will be scored on a 0-3 numbered scale. “Rarely or none of the time (less than 1 day)” scored as 0, “Some or little of the day (1-2 days)” scored as 1, “Occasionally or moderate amount of time (3-4 days)” scored as 2, and “All of the time (5-7 days)” scored as 3. Questions 5 & 8 are reverse-scored as “Rarely or none of the time (less than 1 day)”=3, “Some or little of the day (1-2 days)”=2, “Occasionally or moderate amount of time (3-4 days)”=1, and “All of the time (5-7 days)”=0.

Anxiety Scale

The Anxiety Scale (Spitzer, R., Kroenke, K., Williams, J. B. W., & Löwe, B. (2006) GAD-7) is a short scale with 7 total questions addressing feelings within the two weeks prior to taking the survey. There are four options to select when filling out the 7 questions ranging from “Not at all=0, several days=1, more than half of the days=2, and nearly every day=3”. This is calculated by assigning scores of 0, 1, 2, and 3 to the response categories. To maintain the GAD-7 total score, the seven items are summed with total scores ranging from 0 to 21. From these results, it will be possible to determine if an individual experiences menial, mild, moderate, or severe anxiety.

Cyberbullying Scale

The Cyberbullying in Social Media Scale (Stewart et al., (2014) CSMS) is a quick scale used to determine the level of cyberbullying one perpetrates on social media. This 12-question survey will address questions relating to social media and if an individual has participated in actions leading to bullying through any medium. The responses will be recorded as 0=Never, 1=1-2 times, 2=3-4 times, & 3=5 times or more. The results will help better understand how often individuals partake in cyberbullying, whether they realize it or not. The scores range from 0-36; the larger the score, the higher the tendency of cyberbullying on social media.

Results

Body Image

The Body Image Scale (Rowe, D. (2018) BISQ) divides questions into different subscale categories. All of these subscales score ranges from a minimum of 3 to a maximum of 15. From these subscales, in terms of Overall Appearance Evaluation, respondents scored “about halfway true of themselves” in relation to the three questions asked. In terms of Health Fitness Influence, the 3 questions addressing this concern averaged a 9, indicating respondents scored “about halfway true of themselves” in relation to the questions. Concerning Investment in Ideals, the 3 questions addressing this concern averaged a 13, indicating respondents scored “entirely true of themselves” in relation to the questions. With respect to Health Fitness Evaluation, the 3 questions addressing this concern averaged an 11, indicating respondents scored “mostly true of themselves” in relation to the questions asked. Regarding Attention To Grooming, the 3 questions addressing this concern averaged an 11, indicating respondents scored “mostly true of themselves” in relation to the questions asked. With reference to Height Dissatisfaction, the 3

questions addressing this concern averaged a 7, indicating that respondents scored “slightly true to themselves” in relation to the questions asked. As for Fatness Evaluation, the 3 questions addressing this concern averaged a 7, indicating that respondents scored “slightly true to themselves” in relation to the questions asked. Concerning Negative Affect, the 3 questions addressing this concern averaged a 3, indicating that respondents scored “not at all true to themselves” in relation to the questions asked. Regarding Social Dependence, the 3 questions addressing this concern averaged a 12, indicating respondents scored “mostly true to themselves” in relation to the questions asked.

Based on the BSIQ, certain subscales rank higher than others, confirming that we need to look at the average among all of these subscales. After calculating the total, I determined the average to be approximately 9.25, indicating that through the BSIQ, respondents scored “halfway true of themselves” across the 27 questions asked.

The Body Image Scale, Qualtrics (2024)

Social Media Usage

Using The Exploratory Factor Analysis (Gupta, S., Bashir, L. (2018) EFA) scale, a total of 18 questions were asked to gauge our respondents' overall social media usage. Questions are divided into dimensions of social media usage for educational, socialization, entertainment, and informativeness purposes. Based on the average of all the questions added up, the majority of questions in all categories were answered with a 3.33, indicating “sometimes” when asked about

the frequency of time spent on social media for educational, social, and informative purposes. However, for questions addressing entertainment purposes, the majority answered with “always”, indicating that entertainment is clearly driving the amount of time spent on social platforms.

Statements 28 through 46 are all related to you and your social media usage. Read each statement carefully, and use the rating scale below to indicate how true the statement is for you. 137

The Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), Qualtrics (2024)

Depression

The Center for Epidemiologic Studies Short Depression Scale (Radloff, L. (1977) CES-D-R-10) measures an individual's depression levels. This scale consists of 10 questions directed at individuals to gauge the way they behave and feel. Based on the average of all the questions, the total came out to 1.7, or approximately 2. From this, we can conclude that the majority of the respondents answered with a 2, indicating that the way they felt was “Occasionally or a moderate amount of time (3-4 days)”. This result signifies the average level of depression among these college students.

Statements 47 through 55 is a list of ways you may have felt or behaved. Please indicate how often you have felt this way during the past week by checking the appropriate box for each question. 137

The Center for Epidemiologic Studies Short Depression Scale (CES-D-R-10), Qualtrics (2024)

Cyberbullying

Using The Cyberbullying in Social Media Scale (Stewart et al., (2014) CSMS), we are able to determine the likelihood of cyberbullying occurring within this sample. This 12-item questionnaire social media questions and whether participants participate in cyberbullying. Out of the data collected, over 85% of respondents answered with “Never” indicating a lower tendency to take part in cyberbullying or insulting someone on social media. About 15% of respondents said that they have taken part in some form of cyberbullying at least 1-2 times.

The Cyberbullying in Social Media Scale (CSMS), Qualtrics (2024)

Anxiety

Lastly, The Anxiety Scale (Spitzer, R., Kroenke, K., Williams, J. B. W., & Löwe, B. (2006) GAD-7) asked questions that relate to how respondents have been feeling within the past two weeks prior to taking the survey. Results indicate that the average response of 5 between all questions asked, demonstrating that students have experienced several days of anxiousness within the past two weeks. This suggests a majority of respondents are experiencing mild to moderate anxiety based on the established scale.

Over the last two weeks, how often have you been bothered by the following problems? 137

The Anxiety Scale (GAD-7), Qualtrics (2024)

Discussion

The survey results show that participants' average time spent on social media sites was approximately 5.7 hours a day, translating into almost 40 hours per week spent consuming content on different social media platforms. 39% of users spend most of their time on TikTok, followed by 38% on Instagram. 31% of these students use social platforms for educational purposes. In conclusion, the cross-sectional data indicate a positive relationship between the impact social media has on college students' physical, psychological, and social well-being.

Hypothesis 1: Social media usage impacts the mental health of college students by increasing symptoms of anxiety and depression.

The literature review demonstrates that psychologically, there exists a clear link between social media usage and anxiety disorders, depression, academic performance, career development, and overall mental health issues. These issues can develop from multiple things, but the media has a considerable impact on anxiety levels. With the stigma around mental health, most cases remain undiagnosed as students go to social media to connect with others and find the support they desperately need. Based on the CES-D-R-10 Scale, data concludes that the majority of the respondents feel symptoms of depression about 3-4 days within a week, confirming that

there remains a positive relationship between depression and social media use of college students. Social anxiety remains prevalent among college students in general and has been seen to only get worse with time. Furthermore, with the GAD-7 Scale results, social media possesses a clear representation of the anxiousness that is felt by students through the increase in time spent online, due to societal and internal media pressures.

Hypothesis 2: An increase in social media usage has negatively impacted students' body image.

In terms of physical effects, we additionally see that the more social media consumed, the higher the likelihood of experiencing lower self-esteem, body dissatisfaction, and an overall negative evaluation of body image, confirming hypothesis 2. With the exposure of "thin-ideal" influencers, a high social comparison remains, leading to insecurity and lower love for oneself. With over 7 million individuals taking part in restrained eating, that remains heavily present in college students today. Furthermore, based on the BSIQ Scale, the average of all subscales indicates a lack of love for our body image. How we view our body image can lead to the physical effects we see today, which are intertwined with the psychological effects we see present throughout this research. The physical impact on our body image can translate into a disconnect between self-love and how we feel about ourselves as students based on the content we were consuming online.

Hypothesis 3: With social media readily available at the fingertips of college students, there has been an increase in cyberbullying.

The social effects of the media have had positive opportunities for individuals to reach out to others online and maintain a sense of belonging. However, the media can also be a dangerous space that damages real-life relationships. With a significant loss of respect for one another, cyberbullying is happening everywhere online, increasing one's likelihood of being

victimized. Data has indicated that the more substantial your presence on social media is, the more likely you will be the perpetrator of bullying others online based on insight from established articles. With the current rise in digital media, this effect is becoming faster and more drastic than previously imagined. From the CSMS results, these strengths claims to instill that respondents of the survey have taken part in some form of cyberbullying before, whether they realize it or not.

Hypothesis 4: Increased social media use will correlate with a decrease in college students' overall morale.

Based on the EFA Scale, data indicates that a small amount of time spent on social media was for educational and informative purposes, whereas a large majority of time was spent on the media for entertainment purposes. Through the research process, it has become clear that entertainment is correlated to content and time consumed on social platforms. This alone can affect a student's overall morale, work ethic as well as academic performance in their everyday life. Based on the results from the survey, the two most popular platforms used were Instagram and Tiktok, representing nearly half of the respondents spending anywhere from 1-12 hours a day on social media in general. Data consumed on entertainment purposes ranked at 59%, fitness purposes at 43%, and 31% combined on either education or news-related content, which continues to strengthen the claims made prior.

Conclusion

Overall, a positive association remains between the time spent on social media and the negative impact on college students. Throughout the entirety of the paper, there are many conclusions as to why social media has such a negative impact through analyzing primary data and secondary sources. In conclusion, the data collected and observed has confirmed that there

remains physical, psychological, and social dimensions concerning the impact of social media. The articles and survey address anxiety levels, depression symptoms, body image, accessibility to the media, social usage, effects on academic performance that the media has played a role in, as well as the frequency of cyberbullying online. This data can be used to back up the proposed hypotheses and investigate social media's growing impact on this new generation of individuals growing up with the digital age being more prominent. With this, plenty of research remains to confirm more substantial results. Still, between the information that was gathered in this research, the results have left insights and conclusions to be addressed, with hopes shortly to continue and carry out more in-depth research.

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